

RISIS

RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE FOR SCIENCE
AND INNOVATION POLICY STUDIES

DOCUMENTATION OF RISIS DATASETS *CWTS publication database*

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1 Basic Characteristics

- CWTS publication dataset. It entails the underlying data of the CWTS LeidenRanking dataset, which is the openly available research performance statistics (leidenranking.com). Within RISIS RCF, these statistics are available for all items in the OrgReg register with a certain amount of publications. A detailed description of the LeidenRanking dataset is provided at leidenranking.com.
- The CWTS publication dataset is a copy of the Clarivate Web of Science (WoS) core database with high quality adjustments/ corrections regarding: author affiliations, citation links, author disambiguation and publication level classification. The license CWTS has for this WoS database does not allow the data to be shared outside CWTS. Visits to CWTS for research purposes are allowed, though.
- Hosted and maintained by Leiden University, CWTS

2 Database content

- The CWTS publication dataset contains all publications from Web of Science core collection processed by CWTS and updated on a yearly basis.
- Web of Science core collection: publications and their references from over 12,000 of the worlds most impactful journals across 254 scientific disciplines.

2.1 Definition and description of observations

- Units and definition of observations : bibliographic data of Web of Science publications (papers in peer reviewed journals)
- Number of observations : more than 50 million publications and their cited references (around 800 million)

2.2 Data acquisition and processing (e.g. data cleaning)

- Data purchased from Clarivate Analytics (subscription, plus commercial use license)
- Data processed for bibliometric use:
 - harmonisation of
 - author affiliation
 - journal name
 - author name
 - Cited reference matching

2.3 Information on all variables/indicators

Variable	Description
Publication ID	Unique publication identifier
Authors	List of authors of a publication
Author affiliations	List of author affiliations
Pub title	Title of publication
Pub abstract	Abstract of publications
Pub type	Type of publication (article, review, etc)
Journal	Journal in which it is published
Volume, issue, page	Volume, issue and page of the journal in which it is published

Publication year	Publication year
Number of references	
Number of citations	Number of citation received until present
Number of author self-citations	Number of citations received until present by one of the authors themselves
Number of authors	
Number of author affiliations	
Cited references	List of cited references
Journal category	Category to which the journal belongs
CWTS publication level classification	Class of the CWTS publication level classification to which a publication belongs

2.4 Sectorial, temporal and geographical coverage

- classifications :
 - WoS Journal categories (254), see Web of Science
 - Aggregated journal categories (Number of categories: 7, 14, 35, see Annex A)
 - CWTS publication level classification (number of categories ~4000) (more information at leidenranking.com)
- Temporal coverage: 1980-present
- Geographical coverage : world

2.5 Quality and accuracy of data

- Clarivate Analytics is responsible for the comprehensiveness of the data. There may be some publications missing but our 25 years of experience with the data tells us that this issue is basically non-existent
- There is the issue of coverage of Web of Science in general. There are other data sources that seem more inclusive. WoS has a strict policy on which journals to admit. In that sense it is transparent and consistent.

3 Technical Specifications

3.1 Information on the data base system

- Data is available at CWTS in SQL server

3.2 Technical variable definition

- There is an extensive description / documentation of all tables and variables/ indicators at CWTS. This documentation may be shared with visiting scholars once a visit is confirmed.
- The entire list of variables and their description is too large to present in this document. Therefore, we included the core table of the database below

Columns

Column	Type	Description
UT*	char(15)	UT code of a publication.
CWTS_DT_NO	int	CWTS document type identifier.
CWTS_SO_NO	int	CWTS source identifier.
PUB_YEAR	int	Publication year.
PUB_MONTH	int	Publication month, calculated as the publication month (where January equals 1, February equals 2, etc.) plus 12 times the publication year.
N_REFS	int	Number of references.
N_REFS_COVERED	int	Number of Web of Science covered references.
N_REFS_1980	int	Number of references since 1980.
N_REFS_1980_COVERED	int	Number of Web of Science covered references since 1980.
N_AUTHORS	int	Number of authors.
N_INSTITUTES	int	Number of organizations in the address list.
N_COUNTRIES	int	Number of countries in the address list.
COLLAB_TYPE	int	Collaboration type (0 = No addresses available; 1 = No collaboration; 2 = National collaboration; 3 = International collaboration.)

3.3 Description of the Entity Relationship Model (if applicable)

- There is an extensive description / documentation of all tables and their relationships at CWTS. This documentation may be shared with visiting scholars once a visit is confirmed.
- The entire data model is too large and complex to be included here. Therefore we present a sample of the data model around the table presented in the previous section.

Relations

3.4 Interfaces for access and to other infrastructures (if applicable)

- SQL server studio
- The integration with RCF is established through the OrgRegID. Each harmonized organization is labelled with such an ID. For each organization with an OrgRegId and with at least a certain number of publications, we will maintain and upload a table with basic statistics (output and impact)

4 Scientific use cases and main references

- All quantitative analyses at CWTS and published in research articles are based on this datasytem.
- Selected list of references to 2018 publications using the dataset
 - Chinchilla-Rodriguez, Z., Bu, Y., Robinson-Garcia, N., Costas, R., & Sugimoto, C.R. (2018). Travel bans and scientific mobility: utility of asymmetry and affinity indexes to inform science policy. *Scientometrics*, 116(1), 569-590. (paper)
 - Colavizza, G., Boyack, K.W., Van Eck, N.J., & Waltman, L. (2018). The Closer the Better: Similarity of publication pairs at different co-citation levels. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 69(4), 600-609. (paper)
 - Costas, R., & Franssen, T. (2018). Reflections around 'the cautionary use' of the h-index: response to Teixeira da Silva and Dobrónszki. *Scientometrics*, 115(2), 1125-1130. (paper)
 - De Fonseca e Fonseca, B.P., Costa Albuquerque, P., Noyons, E.C.M., & Zicker, F. (2018). South-south collaboration on HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment research: when birds of a feather rarely flock together, e25. *Globalization and Health*, 14. (paper)
 - Flis, I., & Van Eck, N.J. (2018). Framing psychology as a discipline (1950-1999): A large-scale term co-occurrence analysis of scientific literature in psychology. *History of Psychology*, 21(4), 334-362. doi:10.1037/hop0000067 (paper)
 - Mahieu, R., Van Eck, N.J., Van Putten, D., & Van den Hoven, J. (2018). From dignity to security protocols: A scientometric analysis of digital ethics. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 20(3), 175-187. (paper)
 - Palmlblad, M., & Van Eck, N.J. (2018). Bibliometric analyses reveal patterns of collaboration between ASMS members. *Journal of The American Society for Mass Spectrometry*, 29(3), 447-454. (paper)
 - Robinson-Garcia, N., Sugimoto, C.R., Murray, D.S., Yegros, A., Larivière, V., & Costas, R. (2018). Scientific Mobility Indicators in Practice: International Mobility Profiles at the Country Level. *Profesional de la Informacion*, 27(3), 511-520. (paper)
 - Ruiz-Castillo, J., & Costas, R. (2018). Individual and field citation distributions in 29 broad scientific fields. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(3), 868-892. (paper)

Annex A List of aggregated journal categories at three levels

Top level (7)

1. ENGINEERING SCIENCES
2. LANGUAGE, INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
3. LAW, ARTS AND HUMANITIES
4. MEDICAL AND LIFE SCIENCES
5. MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS
6. NATURAL SCIENCES
7. SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES

Intermediate level (14)

1. CHEMISTRY, PHYSICS AND ASTRONOMY
2. CULTURE
3. EARTH AND ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES
4. ECONOMICS, MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING
5. ENGINEERING SCIENCES
6. HEALTH SCIENCES
7. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SCIENCES
8. LANGUAGE, LINGUISTICS AND LITERATURE
9. LAW
10. LIFE SCIENCES
11. MATHEMATICS, STATISTICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE
12. MEDICAL SCIENCES
13. MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS
14. SOCIAL SCIENCES

Low level (35)

1. AGRICULTURE AND FOOD SCIENCE
2. ASTRONOMY AND ASTROPHYSICS
3. BASIC LIFE SCIENCES
4. BASIC MEDICAL SCIENCES
5. BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
6. BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES
7. CHEMISTRY AND CHEMICAL ENGINEERING
8. CIVIL ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION
9. CLINICAL MEDICINE
10. COMPUTER SCIENCES
11. CREATIVE ARTS, CULTURE AND MUSIC
12. EARTH SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY
13. ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS
14. EDUCATIONAL SCIENCES
15. ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATION
16. ENERGY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY
17. ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES AND TECHNOLOGY
18. GENERAL AND INDUSTRIAL ENGINEERING
19. HEALTH SCIENCES
20. HISTORY, PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGION
21. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SCIENCES
22. INSTRUMENTS AND INSTRUMENTATION
23. LANGUAGE AND LINGUISTICS
24. LAW AND CRIMINOLOGY

- 25. LITERATURE
- 26. MANAGEMENT AND PLANNING
- 27. MATHEMATICS
- 28. MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND AEROSPACE
- 29. MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNALS
- 30. PHYSICS AND MATERIALS SCIENCE
- 31. POLITICAL SCIENCE AND PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION
- 32. PSYCHOLOGY
- 33. SOCIAL AND BEHAVIORAL SCIENCES, INTERDISCIPLINARY
- 34. SOCIOLOGY AND ANTHROPOLOGY
- 35. STATISTICAL SCIENCES